

UNIVERSITI BRUNEI DARUSSALAM
SCHOOL OF BUSINESS AND ECONOMICS

MODULE:
BM-5302 ORGANIZATIONAL BUSINESS

ASSIGNMENT TITLE:
REFLECTIVE ENTRY – HOW CAN I EXPRESS CONSTRUCTIVE CRITISM TACTFULLY
WHEN MY PARTNER’S VALUES DIFFERS FROM MINE?

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For this week reflective entry on values, I think that expressing constructive criticism on my side requires honest and respect the most important. Having a more transparent criticism but at the same time respecting their values showing that I understand that everyone differs in values. I like having polite discussions where we can comprehend each other's viewpoints without feeling like we are criticizing them. This is because I am emotionally sensitive and I prefer getting critics in a long discussion while being thoughtful.

On my partners point of view, they think that straightforward and mutual understanding is the most important when giving constructive feedbacks. They think that being blunt and straight to the point without any sugarcoating might be more effective in getting the other person to understand faster. Even though their choice of words might sound harsh, they think it is what makes the other person to reflect on themselves and improve faster.

For example, this reminded me during my group project previously, I prefer having lengthy but careful discussions and decision making to make sure everyone was satisfied, meanwhile providing gentle feedbacks. When there was a mistake in the report, or just parts to be fixed, I gave my honest feedback while not being harsh when pointing it out. By using words like “please try to change it whenever you are free.” As well as, giving a lengthy feedback and sentence on how to improve it. I think this builds mutual respect for each other and avoid any conflicts even though it will take time.

However, one of my group members prefer to get things done fast and straightforward which is similar to my partners values. They would be too direct and blunt when giving critics to my part of the assignment. For example, by pointing out that my part on discussion is too general or to improve on this section. Without any comments on improvement and think it will save time without any questions but only getting it done.

From this, I realized that people have different values when it comes to constructive criticism. I learned from this experience that directness and honesty are not the opposite. The difference is in the way they express it with the difference in tone and delivery. I discovered that I can continue to be straightforward and effective while upholding my value of respect. At the same time, I started to see that my teammate's directness was intended to prioritize efficiency on getting it done rather than being impolite.